

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: GUYO****FIRST NAME: ARGATA****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Writing Academic Essays (EUCLID 2021, 7-11)
2. Some rules of the thumb when writing papers (EUCLID 2021, 12-14)
3. American Vs British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

WRITE TITLE GIVEN TO RP

1) INTRODUCTION

It was with an uncertainty that I enrolled in this Doctor of International Public Health (PhD) at Euclid University. But after reading the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack and watching the ACA-401D basic tutorial video I am now at ease. I strongly believe the modality of self-paced training offered by Euclid University is excellent and will lead me to achieve my goal.

The focus in period one of the studies is on language, citation styles, and how to use paragraphs/headings when writing response papers. Indeed, there are always new things to learn.

I have picked five areas for my discussions in this Period 1 Response Paper. The areas are essay writing, some thumb rules when writing papers, American versus British English, plagiarism, and style guide.

2) WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAYS

The first chapter of the ACA-401D course pack for period one deliberates on the basics of academic essay writing. It explains how to write a good academic essay.

Academic essays are essays intended for scholarly writing. They share some kind of formal unique style of the flow, citations, referencing of other works, and advance in new contributions. The essence of writing academic essays is to provide answers to hypotheses and aim to communicate new ideas based on gathered evidence (EUCLID 2021, 7).

I realized that starting early is key to writing a good academic essay. You need to know that you are expected to spend much time thoughtfully reading around the topic and making notes and to define very well the questions to be answered. It is also important to come up with an initial plan which contains your initial thoughts and ideas. This will give a roadmap on how one will gather the answers to the questions (EUCLID 2021, 7).

I understood that after understanding the topic, a lot of time will be spent in reading widely and researching on what to write. I will be guided by asking myself questions such as what is already known about the topic, what do I need to read to write the essay, what materials are useful to my topic and whether the materials can be used to support my answers. While making notes I need to include information source, author's name, date, title, publisher, place of publication and all other relevant materials (EUCLID 2021, 8).

3) SOME RULES OF THUMB WHEN WRITING PAPERS

There are some key rules of thumb when one is writing a paper. Key among them is to ensure that you mention the main thesis of your paper in the first paragraph. This will capture the attention of the reader and will make one be more focused on exploring important aspects of your thesis, and not getting generalized to the point of getting into trivialities (EUCLID 2021, 12).

Remember your focus is to support your arguments and, therefore, as much as possible, avoid sweeping generalities with no substance. This will create suspicion in the reader's mind that you have no substance to write.

The goal of writing an essay is for it to be well understood. Make sure you use short sentences and short paragraphs. To maintain the flow of ideas in the recurring sections, make sure to include connective sentences between sections. Remember that you have to make you are writing simply for the reader to get the idea that you wish to express easily. Make your writing interesting and easily flowing by frequently using active constructions (EUCLID 2021, 13-14).

I agree with the idea of supporting all the assertions you make in your essay by expounding relevant passages. However, avoid quotations, especially if the passage does not play an important role in the paper.

And finally, take all steps never to plagiarize. You can do this by acknowledging the source of your information.

4) AMERICA VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

I come from Kenya which was British colony and is my default choice of language. I have learnt that the main difference between the two language forms are on spelling and pronunciations. The meaning remains the same (EUCLID 2021, 26). I am happy to learn about the two version so that it enables me to stick to the one I use instead of mixing. The key point to note is both American and British English are more similar than different. The difference is mainly attributed to different national histories and cultural evolutions (EUCLID 2021, 29).

EUCLID has given me clear instruction on sticking to one form of language and not to mix the two, and I am happy to learn how to choose on any of them in the video presentation (Cleenewerck 2016).

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is defined as “using a source of the information without giving credit to the author of the information” (EUCLIDE 2021, 34). Collins English dictionary defines “plagiarism the practice of using or copying someone else's idea or work and pretending that you thought of it or created it”. (Collins English Dictionary, 1979). This can be intentional or non-intentional. It is important always to acknowledge the source of information failure, which has implications. I have learnt that plagiarism is wrong and unethical (EUCLID 2021, 37).

It is disrespectful and deceitful if one does not acknowledge the work of others, hence such a person’s work will be worthless (EUCLID 2021, 36).

Personally, I believe the one who does not acknowledge another’s work, yet they have used is not only disrespectful but incompetent, and they should not expect to be accorded any course as authors. I will always desist from plagiarism because it is tantamount to stealing. I do not see the reason why, when on use information from another source, they don’t acknowledge it. It is wrong and must be discouraged at all costs.

I have learnt that I have to acknowledge the source of a quote, paraphrase, statistics, or visuals that I borrow from another source.

In conclusion, I will always properly cite the author and/or source that I got the information from (EUCLIDE 2021, 38).

6) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is defined as a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent (EUCLID 2021, 40). This is important if the finished essay is to be coherent and consistent, and acceptable. It provides a means of documenting basic rules of writing and hence needs to be applied accordingly.

I have learnt that there is no single authoritative source on styles that is understandable. The objective really is to guide in aiding consistency when writing (EUCLID 2021, 41). EUCLID has recommended Chicago Rules (Turabian) for our writings in this course, and I will strive to apply them and improve my skills in using this recommended style.

May I acknowledge the ease with which the response paper template has made my writing easy and consistent by inherently applying the Chicago Rules (Turabian), which is a good starting point for me as a student.

7) CONCLUSION

First and foremost, I am excited that after long delay, I have taken the first step to enrol in my PhD program with EUCLID.

After going through the period one (1) of the ACA-401D, I realized there is a lot to learn in writing essays. The video delivered by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck was an eye-opener for me regarding the basic writing issues I have taken for granted.

I must say that this session has prepared me for the many exciting encounters ahead of me. I look forward to learning and becoming an expert in scientific essay writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *How to write a Response Paper*. Bangui: Euclid University.

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